

можливість порівняння підприємств як у динаміці, так і з конкурентами, дозволяє виявити тенденції розвитку та визначити їхнє відносне становище на ринку. По-четверте, відносна простота математичного апарату робить метод доступним для широкого кола фінансових аналітиків та управлінців.

Однак, слід зазначити, що рейтинговий метод не є позбавленим певних обмежень. Одним із ключових викликів є правильний вибір еталонних значень, який може суттєво вплинути на результати оцінки. Крім того, метод може бути чутливим до складу та ваги обраних фінансових показників. Тому, для отримання більш повної та об'єктивної картини фінансових ризиків підприємства, результати рейтингового аналізу рекомендується доповнювати якісними оцінками та прогнозами.

Підсумовуючи, слід наголосити, що математичні методи, і зокрема рейтинговий підхід, є потужним інструментом в арсеналі як спеціаліста з фінансів, так і менеджера, що дозволяє здійснювати комплексну та об'єктивну оцінку фінансових ризиків підприємства. Детальне розуміння математичної сутності методу, його переваг та обмежень, а також грамотне застосування на практиці, є запорукою прийняття обґрунтованих управлінських рішень, спрямованих на забезпечення фінансової безпеки та сталого розвитку підприємства в умовах складної та мінливої економічної кон'юнктури.

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A RECONFIGURATION OF THE CONCLUSION AND EXECUTION OF CONTRACTS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI): IF WE (NO LONGER) NEED THE WILL OF THE CONTRACTING PARTIES

Abstract. Articolul își propune să analizeze unele aspecte privind impactul major pe care îl are inteligența artificială (IA) asupra modului în care se încheie și se execută contractele, prin avantajele utilizării inteligenței artificiale (privind reducerea timpului, eficiență bazată pe interacțiuni rapide, reducerea riscurilor umane, detectarea riscurilor, automatizare), dar și prin riscurile utilizării IA în contracte (care privesc uneori imposibilitatea de a înțelege un context specific legat de încheierea sau executarea unui contract, funcționarea unui sistem care se bazează doar pe anumite date pe care a fost antrenat, care ar putea fi uneori părținitor sau ar putea propune soluții riscante, prin problemele legate de asumarea responsabilității pentru erorile sistemului și eventual influențarea sau chiar înlocuirea voinței părților contractante), precum și limitele utilizării IA în contracte (privind eventualele erori determinate de algoritmi sau

de defecțiuni tehnice, securitatea datelor, confidențialitatea datelor și chiar o dependență de date). Inteligența artificială va fi utilizată în contracte în viitor și va reconfigura modul tradițional de negociere, încheiere și executare a contractului prin faptul că va deveni un instrument intens utilizat de specialiștii din domeniul juridic, ca instrument de sprijin, iar rolul acestora va muta pe zona de supraveghere, interpretare, verificare și considerăm că va fi obligatoriu ca rolul acestora să fie sporit pentru a se asigura că sunt respectate limitele etice și responsabilitatea cu privire la folosirea inteligenței artificiale în contracte.

Abstract. The article aims to analyze some aspects regarding the major impact that artificial intelligence (IA) has on the way contracts are concluded and executed, through the advantages of AI (regarding time reduction, efficiency based on rapid interactions, reduction of human risks, risk detection, automation), but also through the risks of using AI in contracts (which sometimes concern the impossibility of understanding a specific context related to the conclusion or execution of a contract, the operation of a system that is based only on certain data on which it was trained, which could sometimes be biased or could propose risky solutions, through the problems related to assuming responsibility for system errors and possibly influencing or even replacing the will of the contracting parties) as well as the limits of using AI in contracts (regarding possible errors determined by algorithms or technical failures, data security, data confidentiality).

Artificial intelligence will be used in contracts in the future and will reconfigure the traditional way of negotiating, concluding and executing the contract by becoming a tool intensively used by legal specialists as a support tool, and their role will shift to the area of supervision, interpretation, verification, and we believe that it will be mandatory for their role to be increased to ensure that ethical boundaries and responsibility regarding the use of artificial intelligence in contracts are respected.

Considerations regarding the use of artificial intelligence in contracts and its influence on people. Businesses are directly influenced by the use of artificial intelligence (AI) at an impressive level, which is reconfiguring the way business is conducted by representing an essential component for modern businesses. The success of the use of artificial intelligence in business (for example, by automating and optimizing processes, by predictive analysis, by managing a large amount of data efficiently) is based on the understanding that it is necessary for artificial intelligence to function in close connection with human thinking and only on the basis of human intervention to ensure a contractual balance, to be able to respond to ethical and legal challenges and to ensure a use of AI that is safe, without risks to people and that allows the development of society.

The EU Regulation on Artificial Intelligence, which entered into force on 1 August 2024 (known as the AI Law, proposed by the European Commission in April 2021), is the first European Union (EU) law to regulate AI with the aim of enabling its development and fostering innovation while safeguarding the fundamental rights and freedoms set out in the EU Treaties and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and will apply 24 months after its entry into force. It promotes the

adoption of trustworthy and human-centric AI²⁴, with the aim of serving people as a tool and enhancing human well-being²⁵.

The AI Regulation places emphasis on the supervision of AI systems by humans, rather than by automated processes²⁶. The AI Regulation establishes a system for classifying AI according to risks (four risk levels: minimal or non-existent risks, limited risks, high risks, acceptable risks²⁷), and each risk level imposes certain compliance requirements and involves certain security measures, the purpose of such a system being to ensure safe and transparent AI, which respects the interest of people and is centered on trust.

The use of artificial intelligence in contracts and the reconfiguration of contract conclusion and execution: the role of the will of the contracting parties

Essential for a contract is the agreement of wills between two or more persons (art. 1.166 Romanian Civil Code); each party has its own will. The question arises whether the will of a party could be absorbed or replaced by the AI system at the stage of negotiating a contract, at its conclusion or execution, and the answer is negative.

Consent must be serious, free and expressed with knowledge of the facts (art. 1.204 Romanian Civil Code). These conditions must also be respected if the parties' agreement refers to the conclusion of a contract using AI and the concluded contract must reflect the real will of the parties, even if the contract or some clauses are automatically generated by AI, without human intervention.

For informed consent, the parties must know that they are interacting with an AI system and must be informed of this (an obligation to inform), and then they must understand how the AI system works and what its role is. Otherwise, the contract is not valid because we cannot speak of valid consent. We emphasize that this is a consent of the contracting party and not of the AI system. Moreover, if the party on whose behalf the AI system acted does not understand how the AI system worked, does not understand how the AI acted and concludes a contract but does not understand it, we cannot consider the contract valid. It depends on whether we accept that the role of the contracting party in the contract is replaced by the AI system and the will of the party is “established” by the AI system, and the answer must be negative, both in terms of the will expressed by each party and the moment of agreement of wills between the parties.

The artificial intelligence system cannot generate consent, but only externalize manifestations of will²⁸.

²⁴ Recital 1, Recital 2, Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689> (01.05.2025);

²⁵ Idem, Recital 6;

²⁶ European Parliament, AI Act: first regulation on artificial intelligence, 09.06.2023, last updated 20.02.2025, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/ro/article/20230601STO93804/legea-ue-privind-ia-prima-reglementare-a-inteligentei-artificiale#reglementarea-ia-n-europa-primul-cadru-cuprinztor-4> (01.05.2025);

²⁷ European Council, Council of the European Union, Explainers: Artificial intelligence act, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/policies/artificial-intelligence/>;

²⁸ Andrei săvescu, Despre consimțământul exprimat de personoid. Considerații privind Inteligența Artificială și consimțământul, 27.01.2023, Par 1, <https://www.juridice.ro/817970/despre-consimtamantul-exprimat-de-personoid-consideratii-privind-inteligenta-artificiala-si-consimtamantul.html> (01.05.2025);

The party's consent must be free, but it may be flawed if the (previously trained) AI system uses certain techniques that can be seen as flaws in consent: omitting essential information at the time of negotiations, system errors at the time of concluding the contract, or even influencing the will of the contracting party through various manipulation techniques that determine, for example, the acceptance of abusive clauses.

Conclusions artificial intelligence and the impact on the will of the parties in contracts. The risk-based approach of the AI Regulation requires the existence of rules that contribute to the development of trustworthy, human-centred and ethical AI, that ensure a balance between the contracting parties and that prioritize the will of the contracting party and the consent of the parties when concluding the contract. In the guidelines of the Independent High-Level Expert Group on AI appointed by the European Commission, the expert group stressed that AI must be human-centred, AI must be used in the interest of humanity, with the objective of improving human well-being, and that trustworthy and ethically sound AI is necessary, and for this, among other things, human involvement and oversight are required as a well-defined principle²⁹.

Thus, the role of the will of the parties must remain essential where AI systems are used for the conclusion of the contract and subsequently for the execution of the contract, without AI being able to replace the will of the parties, but to assist them in the negotiation, conclusion or execution of a contract, as a support tool.

AI is a tool that can be used to negotiate, conclude and execute contracts (this is not prohibited), to generate, to quickly identify certain aspects, to automate processes and to streamline the process, but it cannot replace the manifestation of the will of the contracting party, and the use of AI must be correct, fair, transparent and above all, supervised and controlled by the human factor. It is the human who must continue to remain at the center of the decision in the contractual plan, and AI cannot replace the will of the contracting party, even in the context of a technological revolution regarding AI, but viewed from the perspective of technology ethics, and it cannot distort the will of the parties, even if this would be used in the interest of the party on whose behalf the AI acts.

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STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF CONSOLIDATION PROCESSES IN THE BANKING SYSTEM

The rationalisation of the market economy and the banking system implies its transformation and consolidation, taking into account the principles of market self-organisation of banking institutions. In order to study the development of consolidation processes in the banking industry, we believe it is advisable to identify the necessary statistical indicators that allow us to assess the degree and speed of bank concentration as a result of corporate consolidation:

- indicators of market (industry) concentration: concentration ratio (CR), Herfindahl-Hirschman index (HHI), ranked concentration index (Hoff-Tydmann index, Rosenbluth index);

- indicators of inequality (unevenness) in the distribution of market shares of its participants: Gini coefficient, Atkinson index, entropy index, Theil coefficient, coefficient of variation, etc.

Let us consider in more detail the essence and procedure for determining concentration indicators in order to identify the most appropriate ones for assessing the degree of concentration and consolidation of the Ukrainian banking sector.

The concentration ratio (CR) shows what share of the market is held by the largest market participants and is defined as follows [1]: